

FACIAL RECOGNITION METHOD FROM IMAGES

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Abstract: While network technology is convenient for our daily life, the problems that are exposed are also endless. The most important thing for everyone is information security. Human beings perform face recognition automatically every day and practically with no effort. Although it sounds like a very simple task for us, it has proven to be a complex task for a computer, as it has many variables that can impair the accuracy of the methods, for example: illumination variation, low resolution, occlusion, amongst other.

In computer science, face recognition is basically the task of recognizing a person based on its facial image. It has become very popular in the last two decades, mainly because of the new methods developed and the high quality of the current videos/cameras.

Keywords: Android, security and privacy, authentication, fingerprint, API.

Introduction

Note that face recognition is different of face detection:

— **Face Detection:** it has the objective of finding the faces (location and size) in an image and probably extract them to be used by the face recognition algorithm.

— **Face Recognition:** with the facial images already extracted, cropped, resized and usually converted to grayscale, the face recognition algorithm is responsible for finding characteristics which best describe the image.

The face recognition systems can operate basically in two modes:

— Verification or authentication of a facial image: it basically compares the input facial image with the facial image related to the user which is requiring the authentication. It is basically a 1x1 comparison.

— Identification or facial recognition: it basically compares the input facial image with all facial images from a dataset with the aim to find the user that matches that face. It is basically a 1xN comparison.

Which are used and where?

They can be used either separately or together and it is best to look at industries that each are applied too.

Facial Recognition:

1) A good example is Facebook, we all have seen the box come up around faces or friends and family in our pictures and the “auto-tag” of that user.

2) Casinos: “The eye in the sky” as they say when you are in Vegas. Most resorts have this in place to scan faces as they enter the casino. This is done to stop people on voluntary exclusion lists or known cheaters that were blacklisted.

3) Financial Services (banks, cryptocurrency exchanges): Facial recognition is used for account openings and online account access.

4) Retail: Face recognition is applied to know when shoplifters or retail criminals enter establishments with history of theft.

Next lets look at the process flow and how facial recognition works:

1) The image is captured in the form of a selfie or from a crowd, the more direct on then the better the results for analysis.

2) Microsoft Cognitive Services say they use ~30 facial points for each face in the image, as well as attributes that include age, gender, emotion, pose, smile and facial hair. This is also known as the “T” zone of the human face.

3) Next the image is compared to the database it is being applied too; this can be a document like in know-your-customer (kyc) processes.

4) Decision time: All the variables that were mentioned in step 2 can be some in the codebase, but what comes out is the percentage to match images. The systems are evolving and becoming smarter, but by no means foolproof. Lighting, distance and camera quality are just a few things to really throw false positives.

Facial Authentication:

The easiest way to think of this is when you unlock your Apple Iphone or Android Device.

You just received that shiny new device (hopefully purchased with cryptocurrency) and are prompted through the oblong-shaped circle to put your head onto the screen, while the facial points are made and stored. After these points are recorded centrally on that device; every time you unlock your phone with your face, this becomes your password or authentication.

Now we are getting somewhere, facial recognition drives the user facial authentication in a few steps. Let’s look at it from a process we have all most likely done before (KYC):

- 1) Capture a picture from driver license or identification card;
- 2) Take a selfie, using technology that ensures it is not stored and live at the moment helps spoofing and false positives;
- 3) The facial recognition goes to work and compares the images through algorithms and renderings;
- 4) Confirm the digital identity and the customer is allowed access.

Face Detection and Recognition Model Based on the FaceNet model

We will use Python and its libraries to find out who the person in the picture is.

Useful python libraries:

1. TensorFlow-Keras version 2.3.1 to predict model load, embedded;
2. Open CV for photo taking, resize and various operations and to take the face out of the picture;
3. Numpy Library for Calculating Mathematics;
4. Any Python IDE (for example - Jupyter notebook).

How to install Tensorflow and Opencv?

We will install libraries with pip commands.

If there is no pip, then you need to install pip. To see if your PC has pip, give this command in the Python shell Windows:

```
python -m pip --version
```

If the correct pip version shows continue.

Installing Tensorflow

To install Tensorflow, this command needs to be run on your command prompt/terminal.

```
pip install tensorflow
```

it is expected that tensorflow will be installed normally.

TensorFlow is associated with the Keras Library

Installing OpenCv

In order to install an open CV, run the command given below:

```
pip install opencv-python
```

Face detection: Separating parts of the face from the picture

Look at the picture 1, here's Barak Obama and his wife Michelle Obama.

Pic 1. Barack Obama and Michelle Obama

So here we are looking at two pictures of faces. If we want to identify these two pictures on the computer, we have to first separate the faces of both of them. We can do this using Python opencv. We will use different features of our faces to identify faces. We call them Hare features. Let's look at the python code below:

```
import numpy as np
import cv2

face_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier('haarcascade_frontalface_default.xml')

img = cv2.imread('obama_photo.jpg')
gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
faces = face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.2, 5)
for (x,y,w,h) in faces:
    img = cv2.rectangle(img,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(255,0,0),2)
    face = img[y:y+h, x:x+w]

cv2.imshow('img',img)
cv2.waitKey(0)
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

Pic 2. Hare features

Save the code to main.py name by creating a specific folder. Download and place the 'haarcascade_frontalface_default.xml' file and the picture, which will appear in the folder as below.

Pic 3. Folder of files

Then we run the **code.py** file on the python shell. For this, you have to give a python code.py command. Outputs such as the following can be found.

Pic 4. The face variable in the code will keep the faces out.

For face recognition, we pass roi_color variable into a function. The rest of the work will do our job. Now we're going to get to the basics. First of all, we have to download the face net model. [The download link is here.](#)

Face recognition: Finding out who the face of the picture is.

Place the model in the folder you main.py file in. Now we have to load the model into our program. For this, we have to import load_model from tensorflow.keras.models. Then we have to load the model on a line as follows.

```
#Loading load_model from tensorflow.keras.models
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model

#Loading the facenet model
embedding_model=load_model("Facenet_model.h5")
```

Pic 5. Loading the models

Now we have to create a function that will load our data from a folder. And his encodings will be filled into a Python dictionary and returned.

Loading the data

We will try to keep it as simple as possible. With a little bit of headwork, we can build a slightly more complex system. For now, we will continue to work with single films.

```
images = {}

images['ben_afflek'] = cv2.imread('data/ben_afflek/1.jpg')
images['elton_john'] = cv2.imread('data/elton_john/1.jpg')
images['jerry_seinfeld'] = cv2.imread('data/jerry_seinfeld/1.jpg')
images['madonna'] = cv2.imread('data/madonna/1.jpg')
images['obama'] = cv2.imread('data/obama/1.png')
images['michelle_obama'] = cv2.imread('data/michelle_obama/1.png')
```

Pic 6. Loading the data

We'll do some work on the data. We will first convert the color channel (BGR2RGB). Then I'll resize the image to (160×160). Then standardize the image and put it back in

```
import numpy as np
def prewhiten(x):
    if x.ndim == 4:
        axis = (1, 2, 3)
        size = x[0].size
    elif x.ndim == 3:
        axis = (0, 1, 2)
        size = x.size
    else:
        raise ValueError('Dimension should be 3 or 4')
    mean = np.mean(x, axis=axis, keepdims=True)
    std = np.std(x, axis=axis, keepdims=True)
    std_adj = np.maximum(std, 1.0 / np.sqrt(size))
    y = (x - mean) / std_adj
    return y
for name in images:
    img=images[name]
    img=cv2.resize(img, (160,160))
    img=cv2.cvtColor(img,cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
    images[name]=prewhiten(img)
```

the images dictionary. That's all. We look at the code.

Pic 7. Converting, resizing, standardizing the image

Our current job is to predict face encodings for our facial images. For this, we will input the image into the model we have placed in `embedding_model` variable.

Dataset face encoding precalculated

We will calculate the embedding for each sample using the `predict()` method of our loaded model object. Let's look at the following code:

```
def l2_normalize(x, axis=-1, epsilon=1e-10):
    output = x / np.sqrt(np.maximum(np.sum(np.square(x), axis=axis, keepdims=True),
    epsilon))
    return output
for name in images:
    img=images[name]
    img=np.reshape(img, (1,160,160,3))
    emb=embedding_model.predict(img)
    images[name]=l2_normalize(emb)
```

Pic 8. Calculating the embedding for each sample using the `predict()` method of our loaded model object

Here we have our image first taken out of the Images Dictionary and reshaped. Here our model was previously trained with dimension data (None,160,160,3). Here we see dimension 4. But the dimension of each of our pictures is 3. For which we have added an additional dimension to do 4 dimensions. Through the next line, we took out the face embedding through simple predict() method call and normalized L2 and put it in the images dictionary.

Extracting image embedding of faces from input images and name prediction

Remember when we were putting the faces out on top of everyone? We will now use the variable which we put the faces out on top of everyone. Before that, we write a function that takes a picture of a face and predicts who the picture is.

```
def predict_name(img):
    img=cv2.resize(img,(160,160))
    img=cv2.cvtColor(img,cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
    img=np.resize(img,(1,160,160,3))
    img=prewhiten(img)
    emb=embedding_model.predict(img)
    emb_norm=l2_normalize(emb)
    minimum_dis=9999
    person=None
    for name in images:
        dis=np.linalg.norm(emb_norm-images[name])
    if dis<minimum_dis:
        person=name
        minimum_dis=dis
    return person,minimum_dis
```

Pic 9. Taking face and prediction

The process is familiar to us until the loop. Inside the loop, we re-extracted the embeddings for each face of the dataset that we had previously calculated through images. The emb_norm here is embedding L2 normalized for new input. However, here we have extracted the distance between the two embeddings with np.linalg.norm and extracted the shortest distance for the image of the name.

```
img = cv2.imread('obama_photo.jpg')
gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
faces = face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.2, 5)
for (x,y,w,h) in faces:
    img = cv2.rectangle(img,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(255,0,0),2)
    face = img[y:y+h, x:x+w]
    name,_=predict_name(face)
    img = cv2.putText(img, name, (x,y),cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX,1,(0, 0, 255))
cv2.imshow('img',img)
cv2.waitKey(0)
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

Pic 10. Passing the picture of our face and writing the name on the picture via `cv2.putText`

Here in `predict_name` function we pass the picture of our face and then write the name on the picture via `cv2.putText`.

So, we have done. The full code of the program is given below.

```
import numpy as np
import cv2

#Loading load_model from tensorflow.keras.models
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model

#Loading the facenet model
embedding_model=load_model("Facenet_model.h5")

face_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier('haarcascade_frontalface_default.xml')

images = {}

images['ben_afflek'] = cv2.imread('data/ben_afflek/1.jpg')
images['elton_john'] = cv2.imread('data/elton_john/1.jpg')
images['jerry_seinfeld'] = cv2.imread('data/jerry_seinfeld/1.jpg')
images['madonna'] = cv2.imread('data/madonna/1.jpg')
images['obama'] = cv2.imread('data/obama/1.png')
images['michelle_obama'] = cv2.imread('data/michelle_obama/1.png')

import numpy as np
def prewhiten(x):
    if x.ndim == 4:
        axis = (1, 2, 3)
        size = x[0].size
    elif x.ndim == 3:
        axis = (0, 1, 2)
        size = x.size
    else:
        raise ValueError('Dimension should be 3 or 4')

    mean = np.mean(x, axis=axis, keepdims=True)
    std = np.std(x, axis=axis, keepdims=True)
    std_adj = np.maximum(std, 1.0 / np.sqrt(size))
    y = (x - mean) / std_adj
    return y

for name in images:
    img=images[name]
    img=cv2.resize(img,(160,160))
    img=cv2.cvtColor(img,cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
    images[name]=prewhiten(img)

def l2_normalize(x, axis=-1, epsilon=1e-10):
    output = x / np.sqrt(np.maximum(np.sum(np.square(x), axis=axis,
keepdims=True), epsilon))
    return output

for name in images:
    img=images[name]
    img=np.reshape(img,(1,160,160,3))
    emb=embedding_model.predict(img)
    images[name]=l2_normalize(emb)
```

```

def predict_name(img):
    img=cv2.resize(img,(160,160))
    img=cv2.cvtColor(img,cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
    img=np.resize(img,(1,160,160,3))
    img=prewhiten(img)

    emb=embedding_model.predict(img)
    emb_norm=l2_normalize(emb)

    minimum_dis=9999
    person=None

    for name in images:
        dis=np.linalg.norm(emb_norm-images[name])
        if dis<minimum_dis:
            person=name
            minimum_dis=dis
    return person,minimum_dis

img = cv2.imread('obama_photo.jpg')
gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
faces = face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.2, 5)
for (x,y,w,h) in faces:
    img = cv2.rectangle(img,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(255,0,0),2)
    face = img[y:y+h, x:x+w]
    name,_=predict_name(face)

    img = cv2.putText(img, name, (x,y),cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX,1,(0, 0,
255))

```

Pic 11. The full code of the program

We should get next at output.

Pic 12. Our output

CONCLUSION

Face Recognition is fascinating on and OpenCV has made it incredibly straightforward and easy for us to code it. It just takes a few lines of code to have a fully working face recognition application. We can switch between all three OpenCV face recognizers by changing only a single line of code. It's that simple. It will be used as an additional security level or feature that makes login flow easier. You will modify this solution, for example, add cryptography to increase biometrics data security. Otherwise, you can try to change the biometrics prompt dialog to your custom layout or whatever you want, but don't reinvent the wheel and use material design documentation for a better user experience.

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